

7 November 72

NB I opened the envelope wherefore the sticky tape

Dear Andrew,

Thanks for your letter. Have you ever heard a song by Tom Lear which goes "... I have a friend in Musid, who has a friend in Puid, who has a friend in Oruid and another one in Tausid and so from Tausid to Oruid + Puid, + Puid the word goes skipping along."

I think it would be good if you wrote to Karen, not because I think you must, it seems to me that if we all write to Karen saying "we love you, we wait camp please don't block us + the Ormanis", then Karen becomes the Director General of Permits + Ormanie we ought really to kick the Sir of dirt in the ass + make him stand up on his feet instead of passing the buck of major decisions over to Karen. In other words, I hope you didn't act too contritely to Karen.

Anyhow, inshallah, we'll get there. Probably the best thing to do would be to fly to Orman and be sitting in the D of Inf. office on the same day as Ka however, I can always take up sheep farming. It's hope to be in UK last week of November.

Cheers, Princess sends her best,

Jim.

Best to Martha from both of us.